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PREVALENCE OF NODULAR GOITER AMONG THE POPULATION OF THE SAMARKAND REGION

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the prevalence of nodular goiter in the Samarkand region. The current state and factors influencing the development of nodular goiter in iodine-deficient zones are analyzed.

Keywords: *nodular goiter, solitary goiter, conglomerate goiter, subclinical hypothyroidism, manifest hypothyroidism.*

Introduction

Nodular goiter develops as a result of enlargement of the thyroid gland for various reasons. Usually such enlargement occurs due to the formation of nodules in the thyroid gland. Such nodular formations can be single or multiple.

According to WHO, approximately 200 million people worldwide suffer from euthyroid nodular goiter. In general, according to various estimates, up to 50% of the adult population may have thyroid nodules, and in 2024, the total number of patients in the Samarkand region was 306 patients.

The aim of the study: to study the prevalence of thyroid nodules in the Samarkand region based on patient visits to the outpatient clinic of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Endocrinology named after Academician Y.Kh. Turakulov in 2024.

Materials and methods of the study: outpatient cards of 60 patients who visited the clinic in 2024 and were diagnosed with nodular or multinodular goiter were studied. All patients underwent thyroid ultrasound and thyroid hormones free T4 and pituitary hormone TSH were tested.

Results: during examination of thyroid function, the average level of TSH was 3.2 ± 3.6 μ IU/ml, free T4 15.3 ± 15.8 pmol/l. 70% (42) of patients were euthyroid (TSH 1.4 ± 2.9), 18% (11) had subclinical hypothyroidism (TSH 5.5 ± 6.7), 11.6% (7) had manifest hypothyroidism (TSH 8.2 ± 9.4).

Conclusions: In 42 patients examined with thyroid nodules who sought consultation, there was a thyroid dysfunction in the form of euthyroidism, 11 patients had subclinical hypothyroidism, and 7 patients had manifest hypothyroidism.

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